

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHANDANA P bearing USN 6SU21CS801 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FEMIN GEORGE bearing USN 6SU21CS802 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms UDAYSHANKAR K P bearing USN 6SU21CS803 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARSHA GIREESH bearing USN 6SU21CS804 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146